

INNOVATIVE METHODS MAKES LEARNING ENGLISH EASY

Ruziyeva Munisxon Komiljonovna

an English teacher at Tashkent Academic
Lyceum No.2 of the Ministry of Internal
Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Annotation: This article contains information and recommendations about innovative methods of teaching English and the importance of foreign languages in the education system. The article contains thoughts on the development of attention to foreign languages in our country.

Key words: foreign language, school, innovation, method, method, educational system, professional education, technology, vocabulary, skill.

Innovative teaching strategies are essential for creating an engaging and effective learning environment for students. They help teachers to develop creative approaches to instruction, as well as help students become independent learners. Today, the ability to know foreign languages is becoming one of the integral parts of professional education. Due to the high rate of cooperation with foreign partners among specialists in various fields, there is a high demand for them to learn the language. The ability to use information technologies and modern teaching methods helps to quickly understand new materials. By combining different methods, the teacher is able to solve specific educational programs. In this regard, teachers should familiarize themselves with modern methods of teaching foreign languages. As a result, the ability to choose the most effective methods to achieve one's goals is formed. The use of several methods of teaching and learning will give effective results. Teaching is carried out in small steps and is based on the student's existing knowledge system. As time progresses, innovations in every field are increasing. Different styles are also emerging in language teaching. A step-by-step approach to teaching English based on the learner's potential, level, and age gives good results. In this case, students are divided into groups based on teaching at the primary level,

teaching at the middle level, and teaching at the higher level. A special program is developed by the teacher for each stage. At the initial stage, important attention is paid to pronunciation. According to Harmer, the first requirement of native speakers during the conversation is pronunciation. At the beginning of the learning process, the teacher should focus on the student's pronunciation. Grammar and vocabulary are important, but if the speaker's pronunciation is wrong, it's all worthless. Native speakers can understand speech even with grammatical errors if the speaker pronounces the words correctly. Therefore, in teaching, the main focus is on pronunciation. In this case, using different audios of native speakers gives good results. The teacher should teach the correct pronunciation of letters and words during the lesson. At the initial stage, great attention is paid to the development of oral speech and reading techniques. If we consider the types of speech activities of teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to perform the following tasks when teaching them: Creating a reading mechanism; Developing oral reading techniques; Teaching to understand what he has read. In addition, students at the elementary level The Present indefinite Tense., The Past indefinite Tense. It is required that they know the tenses of the verbs such as The Future indefinite Tense and be able to clearly use the verb forms in these tenses. Students learn to use singular and plural nouns, to add suffixes "s" or "es" to the third person singular form of verbs in the present indefinite tense, to learn interrogative, negative and command forms of sentences at the initial stage. they acquire during their studies. Language teaching programs on computers and phones are also a good help for language teaching at the primary and secondary levels. Talk (English speaking practice), Daily English, Learn English (English master), How to speak real English are examples. These programs are structured in such a way that they include reading, listening, and test sections. Another good way to practice is to record the new words you have learned and listen to them in your spare time. In addition, showing more movies and cartoons with subtitles in English is also an effective way to teach the language. Preparation of additional text topics using the press, periodicals, mass

media, internet materials can be given as homework. Students will be interested in texts about interesting research and scientific discoveries. In conclusion, it should be said that teaching a modern language is aimed at forming a more cultured person, who has the skills of self-analysis and systematization of new knowledge. Innovative methods are an integral part of the modernization of the entire system. This ensures that teachers can familiarize themselves with the most advanced approaches and then integrate them and use them in their work to achieve significant growth in the education system. Many organizations are moving to a new level by using multimedia capabilities to send and receive information. The use of computers and other devices determines the success of the entire educational process. Sufficient attention should be paid to the formation of speech skills and the development of social flexibility in the trainings conducted during the educational process. In addition, the success of each lesson in education largely depends on the correct organization of the training. The lesson should be based on the creative cooperation of the teacher and the student. Only then will students be able to think independently and will be educated.

The rapid growth of technology has brought lots of innovations in education. And the next stimulating, enjoyable and productive way of learning is from films. Using audio-visual tools to facilitate the teaching process can be productive and fruitful. As defined by Jane Sherman: ‘films are an inclusive piece of students’ lives today so it makes perfect sense to integrate them into the language classroom’ ,it follows that films are a useful means for learners to listen to authentic spoken communication and be exposed to various features of speaking such as vocabulary, pronunciation, voice modulation and accent. There are a number of educational films and teachers could use them to initiate or stimulate discussion about a certain focus area. (It can be different movies; science fiction, cartoon, western or rom com, it depends on the level and the age. Trying to understand a student does his best, and of course while working he is motivated by teacher. And the main thing is developing their listening and speaking abilities .Every teacher can adopt this

technique for himself. For instance to add speaking part after watching a movie, so you can give any task- to write the meaning of the part they have watched already). In order to solve problems and have innovative activities to reach out to students, an instructor has to be creative. Creativity is the process of turning imaginative ideas into reality. For this, creativity involves two processes: thinking, then producing; and adds that innovation is the production or implementation of an idea, so here we talk about critical thinking, that is one's ability to deeply evaluate how you see things, especially problems and difficult situations, for one thing this technique is close to a psychological approach, but widely spread in methodology particular in teaching language. Using Critical thinking you can develop strategies like speaking skill, and there are lots of benefits like: it enhances creativity, it reinforces problem solving ability, develop a number of skills as analytical thinking, evaluative skills, logical thinking and etc.

Well, as you can see the role of innovative techniques and methods which were given above not only motivate learners, as well as due to them they can improve first of all the main four skills which are very important in knowing a language.

Used literature:

1. Qodirberganovna, A. N. РОЛЬ ПРЕПОДАВАТЕЛЕЙ И СТУДЕНТОВ В КОММУНИКАТИВНОМ МЕТОДЕ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ЯЗЫКА В КЛАССЕ THE ROLE OF TEACHERS AND STUDENTS IN COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING CLASSROOM. *Журнал выпускается ежемесячно, публикует статьи по гуманитарным наукам. Подробнее на, 45.*
2. Adamboeva, N. (2023). ASPECTS OF AXIOLOGICAL LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS. *Collection of scientific papers «SCIENTIA»*, (March 10, 2023; Valencia, Spain), 163-166.
3. Qodirberganovna, A. N. (2023). Representation of Maximums in Axiolinguistic Evaluation of Politeness Category in Uzbek and English Languages. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769)*, 1(6), 39-41.

4. Adamboeva, N. (2023). XUSHMUOMALALIK KATEGORIYASINI AKSIOLINGVISTIK JIHATDAN TASNIFLASH NAZARIYASI. *Interpretation and researches*, 1(7).
5. Mirzayeva, G. S. (2022). Realiyaning Nutqimizdagi Milliy Va Madaniy Koloritini Ifodalashdagi O‘rni. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 30, 349-351.
6. Shohsanam, S. K. (2023). O‘QITUVCHI MULOQOT XULQINING ICHKI FUNKSIONALLASHUVIDA OVOZNING O‘RNI. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(6 Part 6), 177-179.
7. Kakharova, S. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF EFFECTIVE TEACHER’S SPEECH IN THE CLASSROOM. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 1(6 Part 6), 173-176. Султанова, С. Р. (2023). ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ЗНАЧИМОСТЬ ПЕЙЗАЖНЫХ ОПИСАНИЙ В СТРУКТУРЕ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ТЕКСТА. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 1(7), 987-992.
8. Султанова, С. (2023). СВОЕОБРАЗИЕ ЖЕНСКОГО ХАРАКТЕРА В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯХ РУССКИХ И АНГЛИЙСКИХ ПИСАТЕЛЬНИЦ В СОПОСТАВИТЕЛЬНОМ РАКУРСЕ. *Talqin va tadqiqotlar*, 1(11).
9. Султанова, С. Р., & Давлятова, Г. Н. (2023). ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ВАРИАТИВНОСТИ ДЛЯ РАЗВИТИЯ РИТОРИЧЕСКОЙ РЕЧИ. "GERMANY" MODERN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH: ACHIEVEMENTS, INNOVATIONS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS, 9(1).
10. Sultanova, S. R., & Nematov, S. X. (2023). FEATURES OF TURGENEV HEROINES IN THE APPEARANCE OF A MODERN GIRL. *FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES*, 2(16), 113-117.
11. Sevara, S., & Timur, A. (2021). GENERAL THEORY OF LINGUISTIC VARIATION. *Chief Editor*.

12. Sultanova, S., & Akhmadzhonov, M. (2023). THE PROBLEM OF THE «LITTLE MAN» IN RUSSIAN LITERATURE OF THE 19 CENTURE. *Science and innovation*, 2(B2), 52-54.
13. Sevara, S., & Nigina, B. (2022). Degrees of Comparison of Adjective Names in Russian and Uzbek Languages. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 3(10), 105-108.
14. Abdumalik o'g'li, O. R. (2023). Theoretical Aspect of "Synecdoche "As a Stylistic Figure. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(4), 249-254.
15. Abdumalik o'g'li, O. R. Cultural Comparison of Uzbek and English Language Speech Styles.
16. Abdumalik o'g'li, O. R. (2021). THE BRIEF INVESTIGATION OF CONTEMPORARY SPEECH STYLES OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 1280-1283.
17. Vaslidin o'g'li, N. M. (2023). Main Categories of Command Speech Acts. *Texas Journal of Philology, Culture and History*, 17, 85-87.
18. Дадахонова, З. (2023). ТЕСТИРОВАНИЕ КАК СПОСОБ КОНТРОЛЯ НА УРОКАХ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(10), 1970-1973.
19. Dadahonova, Z. (2023). CONTROL OF THE SKILLS AND ABILITIES OF THE STUDENTS. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(10), 106-110.
20. Dadahonova, Z. (2023). CONTROL OF STUDENTSKNOWLEDGE, ITS FUNCTIONS AND PRINCIPLES. *NIDERLAND" INTEGRATION, EVOLUTION, MODERNIZATION: WAYS OF DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION"*, 14(1).